

EXPERT SYSTEM FOR COMPOSITE STRUCTURAL DESIGN WITH OBJECT-ORIENTED LANGUAGE

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ABSTRACT

This paper deals with the fundamental aspects in the development of the expert system for structural design with composites. The computer language used is Smalltalk which is one of object-oriented languages. Basic classes in Smalltalk are constructed having a hierarchical structure, and messages sent to each object of the class are produced. It is found that the expert system developed is very easy to expand its ability by adding new classes and messages, but it is somewhat difficult to make an initial framework of structural analysis since a fundamental processing paradigm not well-structured restricts the extension of the system.

INTRODUCTION

Composite materials have large anisotropy in mechanical properties. Ordinary books on structural analysis and design, however, deal with isotropic materials, and a number of designers who can work on composites is very few. On the other hand, there is a great needs of applications for composite structure in many fields such as aeronautics, automobile, and so on. Therefore the development of an expert system for composite structural design has been a subject.

EXPERT SYSTEM

Expert system is a system which has the knowledge which human experts possess and give proper solutions to many problems in a specified field. The fundamental structure of the expert system is shown in Fig. 1. In developing an expert system, what is most important is the representation of the knowledge.

Fig. 1 Expert system

OBJECT-ORIENTED LANGUAGE

The smalltalk programming system is a programming environment in which the fundamental processing paradigm is to send a message to an object rather than the more traditional approach of calling a procedure to operate on some data, as shown in Fig. 2. This approach, object-oriented programming, qualitatively enhances the design, creation, and maintenance of software system. A great deal of this added power derives from modularity.

Fig. 2 Object-oriented processing paradigm.

For instance, a FORTRAN or BASIC statement '5+9' means that the operation '+' yields the sum of two numbers '5' and '9'. A statement '5+9' in Smalltalk, however, means that the message '+' is sent to an object which belongs to class 'SmallInteger' with the argument '9'. Then the message is understood by its receiver and an appropriate response which is the return of '14' is made, as shown in Fig. 3.

Fig. 3 Example of message sending.

The essential difference is that a operation in a procedure-type language is a specified operation in a whole program, but a message in an object-oriented language can be understood only in the receiver object, that is, each object knows how to respond to various messages. Utilizing this characteristic, a programming with Smalltalk can accept the natural way of human thinking and the easy adding of knowledge.

Much of Smalltalk's power comes from arranging its classes in a hierarchy. Each class has an immediate superclass and possibly one or more subclasses, with class Object at the top of the hierarchy. Inheritance is the Smalltalk capability which allows us to re-use software by specializing already existing general solutions. The subclass inherits the behaviors of its superclass.

Fig. 4 Class and its hierarchy.

When an instance receives a message, it first checks the method dictionary of its own class for a method for receiving that message. If none is found, it searches the method dictionaries of its

immediate superclass, then their superclasses, and so on. If a specialized method is required in a subclass, the overriding of inherited method is still allowed. Message '+' is understood in class SmallInteger and message 'sin' is understood in class 'Float' as shown in Fig. 4.

OBJECT-ORIENTED APPROACH OF STRUCTURAL ANALYSIS WITH COMPOSITES

The important and difficult things in making an expert system with Smalltalk are as follows:

1. What classes should be prepared? And What hierarchical structure should be made on their classes?
2. What messages or methods should be prepared?

To deduce the essential part in answering these questions, a simple analytical problem is considered here. The problem is to obtain the in-plane stiffness, in-plane compliance, in-plane strain, and each ply stress of a fibrous laminated composite plate under any in-plane load. The classes and their hierarchy are shown in Fig. 5.

Figure 5 The classes and their hierarchy.

The messages for the objects considered here are classified into the following categories:

1. Instance creation To make an instance of each class. The methods for giving the geometric dimensions or inherent constants are included. Some examples are as follows:

T300and5208 new (1.1)
 Lamina material:argument1 thickness:argument2 (1.2)
 StackingSequence newOnTotalPlyNumbers:argument (1.3)

2. Accessing To access each instance variable. The instance variable can only be accessed by these method. Examples are shown as follows:

aLamina material (2.1)
 aMaterial modulus (2.2)
 aStackingSequence angleOfPly:argument (2.3)

3. Testing To test an object, for example, Eq.(3.1) tests if the stacking sequence is symmetric or not. The receiver object answers 'true' or 'false'.

aStackingSequence symmetric (3.1)
 aStackingSequence hybrid (3.2)

4. Error notification To notify an error message. The following example displays 'not symmetric' on a display.

```
aStackingSequence errorNotSymmetric (4.1)
```

5. Calculation To perform a simple calculation to yield a variable which depends on basic instance variables.

```
aStackingSequence halfPlyNumbers (5)
```

```
aRectangularPlate area (5.2)
```

6. Arithmetic To perform an arithmetic operation. These methods are very useful since the expression of each method is extremely easy to use and to understand.

```
totalStiffness := halfInplaneStiffness * 2 (6.1)
```

```
averageStress := anInplaneLoad / thickness (6.2)
```

In these cases, an in-plane stiffness has six elements and an in-plane load has three components, respectively, but it is not necessary for a user to be aware of that.

7. Mathematical function To yield a mathematical function.

```
aCompliance := anInplaneModulus inverse (7)
```

8. Analyzing To perform a complex calculation using the above methods.

```
aStiffness := aCompositePlate inplaneStiffness (8.1)
```

```
anOffAxisModulus := anOnAxisModulus rotate:60 (8.2)
```

9. Displaying To display the contents of an object.

```
aStiffness show (9.1)
```

```
anInplaneStrain show (9.2)
```

These messages are defined only for the instance of receivers' classes. Consequently, a same message can play different functions depending its receiver. For instance, the message 'inverse' yields an instance of class Compliance when it is sent to an instance of class Stiffness, and yields an instance of class Stiffness when it is sent to an instance of class Compliance. It should be noted that the difference between the instances of classes Stiffness and Compliance is important since compliance yields in-plane strain when it is multiplied by in-plane load, but stiffness does not.

How a receiver object behaves against a specified message is defined as a method and it is entered in the method dictionary of the receiver's class. The followings are two of the methods which class StackinSequence has.

```
totalPlyNumbers  
"answer the total number of plies"  
^ totalPlyNumbers (10.1)
```

```
halfPlyNumbers  
"answer the half numbers of plies"  
(self totalPlyNumbers even) ifFalse:[self errorNotEvenPlyNumbers].  
symmetric ifFalse:[self errorNotSymmetric].  
^ totalPlyNumbers / 2 (10.2)
```

An instance of class StackingSequence has six instance variables. Those are 'symmetric', 'fromCenter', 'hybrid', 'sandwich', 'totalPlyNumbers', 'angles', and 'materials'. The former four variables are all boolean, that is, they are 'true' or 'false'. Variable 'totalPlyNumber' is an instance of class Integer which is a fundamental class in Smalltalk. Variable 'angles' is an instance of class Array which is also a fundamental. Variable 'materials' is an instance of class Material produced here. Since an instance of class Material has variable 'modulus', 'strength', 'density', and 'cost', where each variable is an instance of respective classes and has several instance variables, an instance of class Stacking Sequence has a complicated data structure. Therefore, complicated behaviors can be produced by sending a simple message with very few number of arguments.

Expression (10.1) is the method of obtaining the total number of plies. It simply returns variable totalPlyNumbers. If the half number of plies is required, method (10.2) is used, where two tests exist.

in the definition of a message, every message can be used, that is, a nesting is available. It causes that the method can be written apparently and briefly. For example, the method for obtaining in-plane stiffness is written as shown in Fig. 6.

```
InplaneStiffnessOnSymmetric
"Calculate the inplane stiffness of a symmetric laminate"

| onAxisModulus offAxisModulus eachAngle plateThickness temp |
stackingSequence _ self stackingSequence.
(stackingSequence symmetric) ifFalse:[
  stackingSequence errorNotSymmetric].
onAxisModulus _ self lamina onAxisModulus.
offAxisModulus _ InplaneModulus new clear.
1 to:stackingSequence halfPlyNumbers
  do:[:index |
    eachAngle _ stackingSequence angleAt:index.
    offAxisModulus _ offAxisModulus + (onAxisModulus rotate:eachAngle)].
offAxisModulus _ offAxisModulus / stackingSequence halfPlyNumbers.
plateThickness _ self lamina thickness * stackingSequence totalPlyNumbers.
temp _ InplaneStiffness new.
temp _ (offAxisModulus * plateThickness) convertToInplaneStiffness.
^temp
```

Fig. 6 Method for calculating in-plane stiffness of a laminate.

Figure 7 shows an example of composite plate analysis. The only thing to do for users of the developed expert system is to write a program like this. Such a program is easy to develop and easy to understand for other people. This program yields the in-plane stiffness, compliance, and strain of a fibrous laminated composite plate of which stacking sequence is [-30/30/-30/30]_S and material is graphite/epoxy (T300/5208), subject to in-plane load where $N_1=3500N$, $N_2=1200N$, $N_6=-100N$.

```
| laminaCF layUp shape composite inplaneLoad inplaneStrain |
laminaCF := Lamina material:T300and5208 new
  thickness:1.25e-3.
layUp := StackingSequence newOnTotalPlyNumbers:8.
layUp symmetric:true;
  fromCenter:true;
  ply:1 angle:30;
  ply:2 angle:-30;
  ply:3 angle:30;
  ply:4 angle:-30.
shape := RectangularPlate origin:(0@0)
  corner:(0.3@0.1).
composite := CompositePlate new.
composite madeOf:laminaCF;
  stackingSequence:layUp;
  geometry:shape.
composite inplaneStiffness show.
composite inplaneCompliance show.
inplaneLoad := InplaneLoad new
  longitudinal:3.5e3;
  transverse:1.2e3;
  shear:-0.1e3.
inplaneStrain := composite
  inplaneStrainOnLoad:inplaneLoad.
inplaneStrain show.
```

Fig. 7 Example for obtaining the stiffness, compliance, and strain of a composite plate.

The result after running of the program shown in Fig. 7 is shown in Fig. 8. This is a hard copy of a display of a computer. The stiffness, compliance, and in-plane strain are displayed on the window of System Transcript. System Browser window and Workspace window are also shown. Smalltalk has a lot of other windows

Fig. 8 Result of the execution of the statements shown in Fig. 6, displayed on a computer CRT.

CONCLUSIONS

An object-oriented approach of the structural analysis of composites is illustrated using simple examples with Smalltalk. It is found that the approach proposed here is very useful for developing an expert system for analysis and design of composite structures. And it is found that the expert system developed is very easy to expand its ability by adding new classes and messages, but it is somewhat difficult to make an initial framework of structural analysis since a fundamental processing paradigm not well-structured restricts the extension of the system.

REFERENCES

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